

Terpenoids: Part XLVII—A New Route towards the Syntheses of Cryptomerion and Ar. Artemisene

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Alkylation of appropriate β -ketosulphoxides with isoprene bromide, coupled with the reductive cleavage of the methylsulphinyl group with aluminium amalgam in aqueous T.H.F., has been employed as a convenient method to obtain the desired intermediary ketones which on subsequent Wittig reaction with methylene phosphorane lead to the syntheses of the title compounds.

For the complete synthesis of a terpenoid by the application of Wittig reaction¹, the preparation of appropriate ketones or diketones²⁻⁶ is a vital step. This problem has been eased by the discovery of β -ketosulphoxides⁷ which are easily accessible materials and can be converted into a variety of compounds⁸. Moreover, it has been recently reported by Gassman et al⁹. that the sulphoxides can undergo mono- or di-alkylations with primary halides and subsequent cleavage of the methyl sulphanyl group with aluminium amalgam⁷ opens a new route for the preparation of desired ketones. We employed isoprene bromide as the alkylating reagent and found that the reaction proceeds quite smoothly resulting in the production of suitable ketones which were further tailored to achieve the syntheses of terpenoids having isopropylidene side chain. This forms the subject matter of the present communication.

Cryptomerion, a monocyclic sesquiterpenic ketone, occurs in nature in *Sugi Wood Oil*¹⁰. The constitution (I) has been assigned to this compound on the basis of its chemical reactions and spectral data¹⁰. Further confirmation of the structure was sought through a synthesis¹¹.

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The present communication reports a new synthesis of this compound utilising β -ketosulphoxide (IV) as the key intermediate as described below :

1-Carbethoxy-4-methyl-3 : 3-ethylene dioxy-cyclohexane (III), prepared exactly according to the procedure described in literature¹² upon reacting with methyl-sulphinyl carbanion afforded β -ketosulphoxide (IV). Alkylation of the β -ketosulphoxide (IV) with isoprene bromide in D.M.F. using sodium hydride as a base (cf. 9) followed by the reduction of alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (which was not isolated) with aluminium amalgam in aq. T.H.F.⁷ furnished the ketal-ketone (V) in 60 percent yield.

The compound (V) when subjected to Wittig reaction¹ with methylene phosphorane yielded 2-methyl-6-(4-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-2,6 heptadiene (VI). The ketal showed an I.R. Spectrum which was exactly superimposable with that of our previously prepared sample¹¹. It was converted to (I) by a two step process involving deketalisation and bromination and dehydrobromination as reported earlier¹¹. The I.R. Spectrum of the synthesised ketone showed peaks at 1685 cm^{-1} (conj. C = O), 1650 and 890 cm^{-1} (terminal methylene) which are comparable to those given in literature¹⁰. The U.V. Spectrum of the compound (I) showed maximum absorption at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} 235$ ($\log \epsilon 3.96$). Literature¹⁰ reports $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} 236$ ($\log \epsilon 3.98$).

N.M.R. Spectrum of the synthesised compound indicates the presence of the following groups :

τ . 3.35 (One hydrogen on the conjugated ketone system), 4.95 (one hydrogen on a trisubstituted double bond), 5.25 (one terminal methylene group) and 8.27 and 8.41 (two methyl groups on double bonds) in exact correspondence with the values reported by the Japanese workers¹⁰.

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in cold and crystallized from ethanol; m.p. $168-69^\circ$ (lit.¹⁰ m.p. $168-70^\circ$).

The diterpenic hydrocarbon, Ar. artemisene has been isolated from Worm Wood Oil¹³. On the basis of its physical and chemical properties as well as spectral data¹³, constitution (II) has been assigned to this naturally occurring hydrocarbon. Vig *et al.* have already

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synthesized this compound through two different routes^{14,15}. However, the alkylation of the β -ketosulphoxide (V) with isoprene bromide followed by other unambiguous reactions affords a new and convenient synthesis of this compound on the following lines :

The bromide¹⁴ (VII) was alkylated with malonic ester to yield the diester (VIII) which was subsequently converted to the ester (IX) through half hydrolysis¹⁶ and decarboxylation¹⁷. The ester (IX) was further transformed to the β -ketosulphoxide (X) by the action of dimethyl sulphoxide exactly according to the procedure reported by Corey and coworkers⁷. Alkylation of this β -ketosulphoxide with isoprene bromide followed by the reductive cleavage of methylsulphinyl group of the alkylated product (which was not isolated) with aluminium amalgam in T.H.F. furnished the ketone (XI). This was characterised through its superimposable I.R. Spectrum with our previously prepared sample.

The ketone (XI) was finally submitted to the Wittig reaction with methylene phosphorane to furnish Ar. Artemisene (II). The structure of final product was established through the comparison of its I.R. Spectrum with that of the natural product¹³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis was done by Mr. B. N. Anand, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. Spectra were recorded on Beckmann IR-5 with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films.

1-Carboethoxy-4-methyl-3 : 3-ethylene dioxy-cyclohexane (III) : This was prepared exactly according to the procedure laid down in literature¹².

1-(1-oxo-2-methylsulphinyl ethyl)-4-methyl-3 : 3-ethylene dioxy cyclohexane (IV) : Methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared from sodium hydride (0.875 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (18 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. An equal volume of dry T.H.F. was added and the contents cooled in an ice-bath. The ester (III, 4.1 g.) was added dropwise with stirring in

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about 10 min. The ice-bath was removed and the stirring continued for 1 hr more. The reaction mixture was then poured into water (100 ml.), acidified at 0° with hydrochloric acid (8 ml.) and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The combined extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to obtain the β -ketosulphoxide as a thick liquid (yield 3.3 g., 70%). It showed the presence of sulphur. However, no attempt was made to isolate this compound and it was used as such for further reaction.

5-Methyl-1-(4-methyl-3 : 3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-4-hexenone-1 (V): Sodium hydride (0.295 g.) in dimethylformamide (35 ml.) was placed under nitrogen atmosphere. To this cooled slurry was added dropwise, during stirring, the β -ketosulphoxide (IV, 3.2 g.) in dimethylformamide (12 ml.) and the stirring continued at ordinary temperature till the evolution of hydrogen gas had ceased. To the cooled reaction mixture was added isoprene bromide (2.2 g.) dropwise and with stirring. The reaction mixture, further stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr at room temperature, was diluted with water (100 ml.) and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to remove the solvent. The alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (3.6 g.) was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (216 ml.). Freshly prepared aluminium amalgam was added to the stirred solution in the form of small pieces and the reaction mixture heated at 65° for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the residual solids washed many times with T.H.F. The filtrate was concentrated to remove most of the T.H.F. and the residue was taken up in ether. The ether phase was separated from water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to leave an oil which upon distillation under reduced pressure furnished (1.9 g., 60 per cent) of the ketone (V), b.p. 180–85/7 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4682.

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1700 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1450, 1375 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1090 cm^{-1} (ketal) and 812, 840 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C} = \text{CHR}_3$). ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 72.14; H, 9.84. Found: C, 72.5, H, 9.68%).

2-Methyl-6-(4-methyl-3 : 3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)2,6-heptadiene (VI): The phosphorane was prepared from methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (3.35 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (8.5 ml.) and sodium hydride (0.2 g.) in sulphoxide (4.2 ml.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen in the usual way. To this was added the ketone (V, 1.8 g.) in T.H.F. (10 ml.). The contents were stirred and heated for 2 hr at 50° and left overnight at room temperature. The contents were poured into ice water (60 ml.), extracted with petroleum ether (40–60°) and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed on alumina (15 g.) with petroleum ether (40–60°, 20 ml.) as the eluent. The ketal (VI) was further purified by distillation, under reduced pressure, b.p. 145–48°/6 mm., yield 1.25 g. (69%); η_D^{30} 1.4923.

Infrared spectrum showed absence of any absorption in the carbonyl region. It had characteristic peaks at 1090 cm^{-1} (ketal), 890 cm^{-1} (methylene), 812 and 840 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C} = \text{CHR}_3$). Other prominent bands at 1645, 1615, 1450, 1375, 1320, 1200, 1175, 1045, 975, 950, and 920 cm^{-1} . Calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.22; H, 10.67. Found: C, 76.67; H, 10.56%.

2-Methyl-(4-methyl-cyclohex-4-ene-3-one)-2 : 6-heptadiense (I) : The preceding ketal (VI, 1.2 g.) was dissolved in acetone (18 ml.) and mixed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (10%, 4.5 ml.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hr., then diluted with brine and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried, the solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to afford the corresponding ketone, 2-methyl-6-(4-methyl-3-oxo-cyclohexyl)-2,6-heptadiene, b.p. 135–38°/5 mm., yield 0.78 g. (78%); η_D^{30} 1.4135.

It showed peaks at 1718 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 890 cm^{-1} (terminal methylene), 845 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond). Other prominent bands at 1650, 1455, 1390, 1315, 1270 cm^{-1} . Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$: C, 81.81; H, 10.9; Found : C, 81.57; H, 10.73%.

The bromo-reagent (P.T.T., 1.5 g.) was added in small lots to the above ketone (0.75 g.) in T.H.F. (9 ml.), the decolourisation occurred immediately. After the addition of 5 per cent sodium carbonate solution, the product was extracted with ether, washed with water till neutral and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the bromo compound obtained was heated at reflux for half an hour with pyridine (15 ml.). After cooling, the contents were decomposed with cold water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dilute hydrochloric acid and again with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was vacuum distilled to furnish cryptomerion (I) as a sweet smelling colourless oil, b.p. 137–42°/5–6 mm. η_D^{30} 1.5058 (Lit. η_D^{26} 1.5050). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$: C, 82.57; H, 10.09. Found : C, 82.36; H, 9.98%.

It was characterised through its I.R. absorption spectrum and N.M.R. spectrum.

Ethyl, 2-carbethoxy-5-(p-tolyl)-hexanoate (VIII) : Diethyl malonate (6.5 g.) was added to a cooled solution of potassium tertiary butoxide (prepared from potassium, 1.6 g., and tertiary butanol, 50 ml). To the resulting potassium derivative was added dropwise the bromide (VII, 7.5 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for 15 hr. on a steam bath. Excess of tertiary butanol was removed under reduced pressure. After adding water to the residue, the organic layer was taken up in ether. The aqueous layer was extracted three times with ether, the combined ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was vacuum distilled to furnish (VIII, 5.1 g.) in 51 per cent yield, b.p. 175–80°/7 mm. η_D^{30} 1.478. (Found : C, 71.05; H, 8.38; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 70.56; H, 8.55%)

Ethyl, 5-(p-tolyl)-hexanoate (IX) : To the diester (VIII, 4.9 g.) was added a solution (5 ml.) prepared by dissolving sodium hydroxide (6.9 g.) in methanol (50 ml.) and the contents left for 24 hr. at room temperature. The solid compound separated was dissolved in water (75 ml.) and the solution washed with ether to remove the unreacted diester. The aqueous layer was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the organic material was extracted thoroughly with ether. After drying and solvent removal, the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure with copper powder to yield 2.9 g. (78%) of the ester (IX), b.p. 140–46°/10–12 mm., η_D^{30} 1.463.

Characteristic I.R. peaks at 1730 cm^{-1} . ($-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$ of ester) and 815, 785 cm^{-1} (tolyl). (Found : C, 77.15; H, 9.18; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46%).

1-*Methylsulphinyl-6-(p-tolyl)-heptan-2-one* (X): The above β -ketosulphoxide was obtained as a semi-solid (2.1 g., 66%) from sodium hydride (0.58 g.), dimethylsulphoxide (12 ml.) and the ester (IX, 2.8 g.) by following the same procedure as described under (IV). It was used as such for the next reaction.

2-*Methyl-6-oxo-10-(p-tolyl)-undeca-2-ene* (XI): Dry D.M.F. (21 ml.) was added to sodium hydride powder (0.185 g.) under an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting slurry was stirred and the solution of β -ketosulphoxide (X, 2 g.) in dry D.M.F. (7 ml.) was added to it slowly and with occasional cooling so as to keep the reaction under control. The contents were kept stirred for some time more till the evolution of hydrogen ceased. This was followed by the addition of isoprene bromide (1.5 g.) dropwise and with cooling. After stirring further for half an hour, 75 ml. of water was added to the reaction mixture and worked up in the usual way, when 2.3 g. of the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide was obtained. This was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (140 ml.) and treated with freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (2 g. aluminium). The oil left after the usual working up and removal of solvent upon distillation under reduced pressure afforded (1.1 g., 55%) of the ketone (XI); b.p. 132–34°/4 mm. η_D^{25} 1.4982.

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I.R. absorption peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}-$); 1450, 1375 cm^{-1} (C—Me) and 815 cm^{-1} (tolyl). (Found: C, 83.69; H, 10.43; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$: C, 83.77; H, 10.36%).

2-*Methyl-6-methylene-10-(p-tolyl)-undeca-2-ene* (II): Methylene phosphorane was obtained using sodium hydride (0.11 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (2.5 ml.) and methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (1.75 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (5 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. To the phosphorane at room temperature was added the ketone (XI, 1 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml.). The stirring was continued for 4 hr. at 60° and then left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water (40 ml.) The organic layer was extracted with petroleum ether (3 × 50 ml.), the combined extracts washed with cold water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed on alumina using petroleum ether (40–60°) as eluent. The hydrocarbon obtained was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure; b.p. 102°/3 mm.; yield 0.71 g. (71%). η_D^{25} 1.5056 (lit.¹³ η_D^{20} 1.5036). (Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}$: C, 88.82; H, 11.18. Found: C, 88.56; H, 11.14%).

I.R. Spectrum of the synthesised hydrocarbon showed prominent bands at 1640, 1515, 1455, 1375, 1108, 1045, 886, 810 and 720 cm^{-1} identical to those reported in literature¹³. U.V. absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 273, 262.2 and 256 $\text{m}\mu$ (Lit.¹³ $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 271, 262.5 and 256 $\text{m}\mu$).

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